

On Fibre Composites with Intermittent Interlaminar Bonding

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ABSTRACT

The concept of intermittent interlaminar bonding is investigated as a means of improving the fracture toughness of angle-ply fibre reinforced composites without significant loss of tensile strength. Both boron/epoxy and graphite/epoxy composites were intercalated with perforated Mylar sheet inlays between the laminae producing intermittent bonding. Full bonding was achieved through the perforated regions and weak bonding existed in the remaining area. The results obtained showed that for such composites the fracture toughness improved by a significant 150-200% and the tensile strength only decreased by 10-25% when compared to the fully bonded control samples. The major mechanism of toughness enhancement is shown to be caused by interlaminar delamination close to the region of fracture.

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that high tensile strength and high fracture toughness are mutually exclusive in conventionally made brittle fibre-brittle matrix composites [1]. Good bonding between fibre and matrix is necessary to achieve high strength but it does not allow the composite to develop its maximum toughness through the various mechanisms of fracture such as fibre pull-out, creation of new surfaces, interface debonding and stress redistribution [2]. In many applications of composite it is not sufficient only to consider strength and stiffness. Fracture resistance, particularly under impact conditions, must also be included in the design process. In recent years there have been some attempts to produce high fracture toughness composites without significant loss of tensile strength. For example, Marston et al. [1] and Atkins [2, 3] have developed the concept of intermittent bonding for high strength/high toughness composites. Essentially the fibres are intermittently coated with a fluid along its length so that intermittent regions of strong and weak bonds and hence regions of low and high toughnesses are obtained. Boron-epoxy composites with fibres coated intermittently with polyurethane varnish give fracture toughnesses over 200 kJ/m² (compared with 50 kJ/m² for plain uncoated samples) whilst still retaining their rule of mixture strength of some 650 MPa [2]. These two attributes are retained even when the composite is subjected to simulated aircraft flight mission environments [4]. It should be pointed out however that the large toughness derived from these intermittently bonded fibre composites arises mainly from the

work dissipated in fibre pull-out. In practical applications the maximum pull-out lengths may not be achieved and therefore the full toughness cannot be developed [5]. Furthermore, it has been found that this toughening method is not as effective in angle-ply composites as it is in unidirectional composites. This is due to the high interlaminar shear and normal stresses set up near the edges during the deformation of angle-ply composites which subsequently initiate delamination and fraying at free edges and around discontinuities. This paper presents a new method of imparting large toughness to angle-ply composites by means of intermittent interlaminar bonding which is implemented using perforated polymeric films as inlays between the laminae during fabrication. These inlays produce a weak interlaminar strength in regions of the film and a high interlaminar strength, typical of the regularly laid up composite, in the perforated areas. It is expected that in the weak regions interlaminar debonding takes place resulting in crack front bifurcation and subcrack propagation along the laminae interface. In the strong regions delamination is discouraged and shear stress transfer is permitted. Some initial work on graphite/epoxy composites with intermittent interlaminar bonding has already been reported [6, 7] and the present work is complementary to these investigations. It should also be noted that the partial interlaminar bonding concept has been recently applied to fibre reinforced concrete and cement mortar [8, 9].

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Materials and Fabrication of Composites

Two types of $\pm 45^\circ$ angle-ply composite materials were fabricated in the laboratory and studied in this investigation. One was a boron/epoxy composite (0/+45/0/-45/0) in which the filaments were coated with a polyurethane varnish of varying repeated lengths (β) over a 50 mm repeat distance and the other was a plain graphite/epoxy composite (0/+45/0/-45/0/+45/0/-45/0) manufactured from prepregged tapes A-S/Epikote 210 supplied by Courtaulds Limited (UK). The perforated plastic inlays were made from thin (~ 0.05 mm) Mylar (polyethylene terephthalate) sheets produced by Du-Pont and were intercalated between the plies at the time of stacking. For the boron/epoxy composites the percentage contact (α) between the laminae, i.e. the proportion of the circular perforated area which consisted of many small holes of 3 mm diameter to the total planar composite area, was fixed at 0.1. For the graphite/epoxy composites the holes were 5 mm diameter and α varied between 0 and 1.0. The nominal fibre volume fractions (v_f) for these two composites were 20% and 60% respectively.

Mechanical Tests

Standard dumbbell shape tensile and compact tension fracture toughness specimens were prepared according to curing schedules given by the manufacturers from these composites and tested in an Instron machine. The elastic modulus (E_C), tensile strength (σ_t), fracture strain (ϵ_f), critical stress intensity factor (K_{IC}) and specific fracture energy absorption (G_C) were obtained from these experiments. K_{IC} was calculated using the maximum load and initial crack length from expressions given in stress intensity factor handbooks [10] and G_C was measured by dividing the total area under the load-deflection curve of the fracture toughness experiments with the fractured ligament area [11]. All tests were conducted at laboratory ambient conditions of approximately 20°C and 65°R.H.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Boron-Epoxy Composites

The tensile strength and specific fracture energy absorption results are shown in Figures 1 and 2. Results for the plain composite are also given for comparison. It can be seen that coating the filament with the polyurethane varnish decreases σ_t but increases G_C . This tendency is more remarkable as β increases. For the uncoated composites (i.e. $\beta = 0$) the effect of interlaminar bonding is to increase G_C from 40 kJ/m^2 to 110 kJ/m^2 but it decreases σ_t from 450 MPa to 400 MPa. This represents a toughness improvement of over 150% with a strength loss of only 10% when compared to the plain composite. As β is increased to 1.0, i.e. the filaments are fully coated, the increase in G_C is

negligible but the loss in σ_t is an unacceptable 40% so that there is little advantage in having the Mylar inlays intercalated with the plies.

Graphite-Epoxy Composites

The G_C and K_C results for the intermittent interlaminar bonded composites are shown in Figure 3 as a function of α . Table 1 also gives a summary of all the experimental results for E_C , σ_t and ϵ_f . Within experimental scatter all the composites failed at approximately 1% tensile strain which is independent of α . Since the graphite fibres fracture with a tensile strain range between 1.08% and 1.24% these results indicate that once the fibres in the 0° plies fracture the whole composite breaks. It is clear from Figure 3 that G_C increases from about 45 kJ/m² at $\alpha = 1$ to a maximum of 120 kJ/m² at $\alpha = 0.2$. But from Table 1 σ_t decreases from 630 MPa to 480 MPa for corresponding α values. The intermittent interlaminar bonding concept is thus an effective method in improving the toughness of the graphite-epoxy angle-ply composite without a significant tensile strength loss. However, there is no advantage in having full sheets of Mylar, i.e. $\alpha = 0$, inserted between plies since the strength loss (both tensile and interlaminar shear) will be too considerable to be of any use. The K_C results given in Figure 3 remain reasonably constant with α so that the crack initiation resistance (K_C) has not been sacrificed in order to obtain improvement in crack propagation resistance (G_C).

ANALYSIS OF RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The elastic modulus (E_C) of the intermittent interlaminar bonded composites may be approximately analysed as follows. By assuming that the graphite/epoxy plies (i.e. the 0° and $\pm 45^\circ$ laminae) effectively constitute one phase and the Mylar inlays form the other phase, then

$$E_C = E_O \left(\frac{t_{ge}}{t_{ge} + t_m} \right) + E_m \left(\frac{t_m}{t_m + t_{ge}} \right) (1 - \alpha) \quad (1)$$

where E_O is the elastic modulus for the fully bonded angle-ply composite (i.e. $\alpha = 1$) corresponding to t_{ge} , E_m is the elastic modulus and t_m is the effective thickness for the Mylar inlays. The composite thickness, $t_C = t_{ge} + t_m$ and the factor $(1 - \alpha)$ is to account for the perforations in the Mylar inlays.

To determine the tensile strength a suitable fracture criterion must be used. From the tensile results given earlier it seems that a constant critical strain (ϵ_C) is an appropriate criterion. Note that this is different to the critical interlaminar shear strength criterion used in [7]. It is observed in this work that the fibres in the 0° plies always break but the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies delaminate without any fibre breakage. The composite strength is thus given by

$$\sigma_t = E_C \epsilon_C \quad (2)$$

Equations (1) and (2) can be used to calculate E_C and σ_t for the graphite-epoxy composites using $E_O = 63$ GPa, $E_m = 3$ GPa, $t_{ge} = 1.19$ mm, together with t_C and ϵ_f values given in Table 1. The theoretically calculated results are also given in the table and they are in good agreement with experimental measurements.

To determine theoretically the fracture toughness of the composites it is necessary to identify all the fracture micro-mechanisms [1, 2]. For both types of composites the $\pm 45^\circ$ plies break with little or no fibre pull-out. The 0° plies for the boron-epoxy composite have longer pull-out lengths (critical length $l_C = 3.5$ mm) than the graphite-epoxy composites ($l_C = 0.2$ mm). The usual toughness contributions as given in [2, 4] are those of fibre pull-out ($G_{p.o.}$), stress redistribution (G_{re}) and creation of matrix surface and fibre-matrix interface (G_s). Thus,

$$G_s \approx (1 - v_f) G_m + \frac{v_f G_{if} \ell_c}{d} + v_f G_f \quad (3)$$

$$G_{p.o.} = \frac{\gamma v_f \ell_c^2}{8d} \times \left(\frac{\text{number of } 0^\circ \text{ plies}}{\text{total number of plies}} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{and } G_{re} = \frac{v_f \sigma_f^2 \ell_c}{3E_f} \times \left(\frac{\text{number of } 0^\circ \text{ plies}}{\text{total number of plies}} \right) \quad (5)$$

E_f , G_f and d are the elastic modulus, fracture toughness and diameter of the fibre; $G_{if} \approx G_m$, the subscripts 'if' and 'm' indicate interface and matrix respectively and γ is the fibre-matrix frictional strength. In addition to the above toughnesses the angle-ply composites fail with considerable delamination between plies and this mechanism involves two additional toughness terms as discussed in [7]. Careful microscopic examination of the fractured surfaces indicates that delamination takes the form of triangular saw teeth in the 45° plies pulling out from the two adjacent 0° plies. The average depth (D) of the saw tooth is the average delamination distance and it increases as α decreases. There is also evidence that D varies with specimen geometry [12]. Before delamination can occur the matrix surfaces between the perforations must be fractured and this specific work is given by

$$G_{ds} = \frac{D\alpha G_m}{t_c} \times (\text{number of interface}) \quad (6)$$

The frictional work in pulling out the delaminated saw teeth is

$$G_{dpo} = \frac{1}{3} \frac{\tau^* D^2}{t_c} \times (\text{number of interface}) \quad (7)$$

where τ^* is the average frictional strength between the plies after delamination has taken place and its magnitude may be determined experimentally. The total fracture toughness (G_c) is given by the sum of equations (3) to (7).

For the boron-epoxy composites $\alpha = 0.1$, $G_m = G_{if} = 500 \text{ J/m}^2$, $\gamma = 10 \text{ MPa}$ when $\beta = 0$ and 2 MPa for all other $\beta > 0$ [2], $\ell_c = 3.45 \text{ mm}$, $d = 140 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, $E_f = 380 \text{ GPa}$, $\sigma_f = 3.45 \text{ GPa}$, $\tau^* = 3 \text{ MPa}$ and from experiments $D \approx 4 \text{ mm}$ independent of β . As given in [2, 4] the fibre pull-out lengths increase with β so that equations (3) and (4) with the values of the various quantities given above are reduced to [2]

$$G_{p.o.} = 27 \left[\frac{0.14}{1 - 0.955\beta} + 2\beta \right]$$

$$\text{and } G_{re} = \frac{2.65}{1 - 0.955\beta}.$$

As β increases these two terms become predominant. However, at low β (≤ 0.2) values the delamination term, G_{dpo} , is the most significant. It contributes about 65 kJ/m^2 to the total toughness. The predicted total G_c results are superimposed in Figure 2 and the agreement with experimental measurements is reasonable.

For the graphite-epoxy composites $\gamma = 10 \text{ MPa}$, $d = 10 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, $E_f = 215 \text{ GPa}$ and $\sigma_f = 2.30 \text{ GPa}$. Because of the small critical fibre length, $\ell_c = 0.2 \text{ mm}$, $G_{p.o.}$ and G_{re} are negligible. The predominant fracture mechanism is that due to delamination, G_{dpo} . Experiments show that the average delamination length

increases from about 2 mm at $\alpha = 1$ to 5 mm at $\alpha = 0$. As shown in Figure 3 the predicted G_c results compare favourably with the experimental data. It should be pointed out here that some preliminary work carried out so far indicates that G_c is geometry dependent [12]. For example, in single edge notched tension specimens, G_c is equal to 210 kJ/m² and 240 kJ/m² respectively for $\alpha = 0.2$ and $\alpha = 0$. These values are larger than the corresponding compact tension specimens (i.e. 120 kJ/m² and 92 kJ/m²). These results may be rationalised by the much larger delamination lengths observed for the single edge notch specimens.

CONCLUSION

The intermittent interlaminar bonding concept has been shown in this investigation to be an effective method to improve the fracture toughness of both boron-epoxy and graphite-epoxy composites. The 150-200% toughness increase is at an expense of some 15-25% loss of tensile strength. This trade-off seems acceptable in many applications. An approximate analysis is presented for both strength and toughness and it gives reasonable agreement with experimental results. It is shown that the fracture energy absorption during delamination is a major contribution to the total toughness of the composites.

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Table 1 Tensile properties of graphite-epoxy composites with intermittent interlaminar bonding

Percentage contact area (α)	Composite thickness t_c (mm)	Experimental failure strain ϵ_f (%)	Tensile strength σ_t (MPa)		Elastic modulus E_c (GPa)	
			Theory	Expt	Theory	Expt
1.00	1.19	1.01 \pm 0.10	630	633 \pm 25	63	63 \pm 6.4
0.50	2.02	1.10 \pm 0.09	420	419 \pm 35	38	37 \pm 6
0.35	1.75	1.02 \pm 0.11	440	446 \pm 20	43	44 \pm 2.7
0.20	1.73	0.99 \pm 0.21	435	475 \pm 39	44	49 \pm 8.2
0	1.97	1.09 \pm 0.18	425	365 \pm 50	39	36 \pm 2.4

FIG. 1 TENSILE STRENGTH OF BORON/EPOXY COMPOSITES (0/-45/0/+45/0)

FIG. 2 FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF BORON/EPOXY COMPOSITES (0/-45/0/+45/0)

FIG. 3 FRACTURE PROPERTIES OF GRAPHITE/EPOXY COMPOSITES (0/-45/0/+45/0/-45/0/+45/0)

